

TIME4CS

SUPPORTING SUSTAINABLE INSTITUTIONAL CHANGES TO
PROMOTE CITIZEN SCIENCE IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

D1.2: Best practices repository of TIME4CS front-runners

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List of Abbreviations

ACSA	Australian Citizen Science Association
AU	University of Aarhus
CODATA	Committee on Data for Science and Technology
CS	Citizen Science
CSA	Citizen Science Association
CSS	The Center for Science Studies, University of Aarhus
CC-CS	Citizen Science Center Zurich
CRIS	Community Research Initiative for Students
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
ETHZ	ETH Zurich
ExCiteS	Extreme Citizen Science, UCL
IA	Intervention Area
FR	Front-Runner
GA	Grounding Action
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LERU	League of European Research Universities
OPAL	Open Air Laboratories
OS	Open Science
PES	Public Engagement in Science
PWA	Participatory Science Academy, University of Zurich
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
SNF	Swiss National Science Foundation
TF	Task Force
UCL	University College London
UZH	University of Zurich
WG	Working Group

Recurrent Links

[University of Aarhus](#)

[Citizen Science Center Zurich](#)

[University of Zurich](#)

[ETH Zurich](#)

[University College London](#)

[ExCiteS](#)

Executive Summary

The current document, titled “Best practices repository of TIME4CS front-runners” has been developed within the framework of the TIME4CS project which is funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101006201.

The main objectives of the document are to:

- Analyse each Front-Runner to describe which actions were required to implement Institutional Changes and to promote citizens’ engagement in R&I activities within their organisation;
- expand the number and the kind of possible Grounding Actions;
- share the best practices of institutional adoption of public engagement and Citizen Science that Implementers can include in their roadmaps.

To this end, the document analyses the history and activity of the Front-Runners since their establishment, and maps their activities with the identified Intervention Areas and Grounding Actions. The result of this process is the identification of the best practices that allowed Front-Runners to succeed in achieving the changes necessary to have Public Engagement and Citizen Science promoted and supported at the Institutional level.

1. Introduction

The overall objective of WP1 is to map and extract knowledge from successful institutional adoption of Citizen Science (CS) in order to codify best practices and lessons learnt as basis for the roadmaps of the implementing organisations. To better understand what actions are required to embed CS in Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), task T1.2 analysed the experience of three Front-Runners (FRs), i.e. organisations with direct experience in Institutional Changes. The University College London (UCL), Aarhus University (AU) and the Citizen Science Center Zurich (CC-CS) all have a comprehensive expertise in the field of CS and Public Engagement in Science (PES). They also have already undergone Institutional Changes in one or some of the so-called Intervention Areas (IAs), such as changes in organisational structures or functions, organization of education/training courses, establishment of contact point, protocols, and dedicated funds, elaboration of new norms or explicit mission statements.

The adoption of CS in RPOs requires a culture of change, and in this particular case a combination of the two common approaches of Institutional Change need to be considered: the social approach and the organisational approach. The social approach looks at social patterns that are modified, requiring a personal commitment of people to change their own behaviours, views and mindsets. In the organisational approach instead, organisational structures such as norms, procedures and protocols are modified. In this case the effort of leaders and managers is important, as while the social approach rather works on a bottom-up basis, the organisational approach is implemented mostly top-down. With these two concepts in mind, and based on recommendations by the League of European Research Universities (LERU), the TIMES4CS consortium has identified four areas in which – alone or combined – Institutional Changes should happen in order to institutionalise PES and CS in RPOs. These IAs are 1) Research, 2) Education and Awareness, 3) Support Resources and Infrastructure, and 4) Policy and Assessment. For each IA several concrete actions are identified, what we call in the following the Grounding Actions (GAs).

Based on a detailed analysis of the history and activities of FRs in relation to IAs and GAs, including some inputs from early work for T1.1, the initial findings were further elaborated and extended with the identification of new possible GAs. The final results include a detailed presentation of the actions and their value as experienced by the FRs which, together with a few underlying and common tactics, provide a wealth of invaluable information to be included in the roadmap of the implementing organisations.

The report is structured the following way: the next sections set the theoretical framework, where we explain in more detail the ideas behind the IAs and GAs and clarify the analysis process. Chapter 2 introduces the three FRs and the history of CS in their organisations. Chapter 3 is dedicated to the GAs including a detailed description and a comprehensive analysis of each action. The best practises are described in Chapter 4 and the report ends with the conclusion.

1.1 Intervention Areas (IAs)

The concept of the Intervention Areas is built upon two papers from the League of European Research Universities (LERU) where specific recommendations about CS and Institutional Change are outlined.

The paper “Citizen science at universities: Trends, guidelines and recommendations”¹ looks at the state-of-the-art of Citizen Science, highlighting recent developments and identifying common trends. After listing some important success factors common to many existing CS projects, it provides a set of guidelines for professional scientists planning CS projects at universities, and a set of recommendations for universities, for research funding organisations, and for policy making bodies.

“Open Science and its role in universities: a roadmap for cultural change”² looks at the pillars of Open Science (OS) and recognizes CS as one of them, inviting universities to adopt and support the methodology.

These existing recommendations helped to identify some potential areas of intervention. In further discussions with the FRs – and based on their expertise – the final four areas were defined more precisely and tailored towards the expertise present in the TIME4CS consortium. They are called Intervention Areas as they show the areas in which - alone or combined - interventions should happen to achieve changes and institutionalise PES and CS in RPOs.

The four IAs as stated in the TIME4CS proposal are the following:

- **Research:** Acknowledgment by the RPOs’ ecosystem of CS as an evolving set of research methods and of its societal and educational benefits, through use of CS in research projects and creation of CS communities of practice;
- **Education and Awareness:** Activities to raise awareness and build capacity amongst researchers, funders and civil society of criteria for successful CS activities in compliance with ethical, legal and privacy regulations. This includes events to promote CS and training programmes within the RPOs (also by establishing links with existing EU projects and training programmes on CS);
- **Support resources and Infrastructure:** Creation within the RPOs of a single point of contact for addressing CS questions and of a system to support researchers implementing CS activities, including support to CS projects for long-term commitment for infrastructure and data repositories;
- **Policy and Assessment:** Assessment of CS contributions and adaptation of research evaluation policies and reputation systems accordingly, taking into account incentives which could foster the implementation of CS activities

1.2 Grounding Actions

For each IA, the TIME4CS consortium has identified a preliminary set of Grounding Actions (GAs), i.e. concrete actions that are recommended to undertake in order to achieve Institutional Changes. These GAs focus mainly on CS and PES, but also the more general concept of OS is taken into account - as Institutional Changes promoting OS are often paving the way to the ones promoting PES and CS.

¹ <https://www.leru.org/publications/citizen-science-at-universities-trends-guidelines-and-recommendations>

² <https://www.leru.org/publications/open-science-and-its-role-in-universities-a-roadmap-for-cultural-change>

Following the analysis process (see Section 1.3 Analysis Process 1.3), the original GAs have been slightly modified and a few additional GAs have been added, which expand the range of possible activities based on the history and direct experience of the FR organisations, as later illustrated in Chapter 3 (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Overview of Grounding Actions per Intervention Area

The original GAs include:

- **Research**
 - To develop research projects using CS methodology
 - To expand running research project using CS methodology
 - To establish/belong to a CS network (international or national associations)
 - To plan or implement changes in organisational structures or functions
- **Education and Awareness**
 - To set up training programmes for researchers and citizen scientists
 - To organize debates or public events to promote CS
 - To establish or to link with working groups on CS
- **Support resources and Infrastructure**
 - To identify an institutional contact point for CS
 - To develop protocols on implementation of CS activities
 - To foresee funds for CS activities
 - To establish facilities to support CS activities
- **Policy and Assessment**
 - To adopt evaluation criteria for researchers' evaluation that take into account CS
 - To adopt explicit mission statements and strategies
 - To develop new institutional norms, regulations, policies or agreements

The additional GA include:

- **Education and Awareness**
 - To set up training programmes for students
 - To set up information sessions specifically for management
 - To set up informal occasion of interactions with researchers
 - To find and nurture “CS champions” both at the management and at the student/researcher levels
 - To develop easily accessible materials (prints, web, media, etc.)
- **Support Resources and Infrastructure**
 - To participate in national or international CS projects (e.g. H2020)
 - To make known and available open and free tools and/or existing tech solution
 - To facilitate the setup of pilots/tests for the methodology
 - To provide ethic/legal protocols tailored to the institutions/national requirements
- **Policy & Assessment**
 - To install reward mechanisms for doing CS

Table 1 in the APPENDIX gives a combined view of all GAs.

1.3 Analysis Process

The three FRs’ history of CS and PES activities has been studied thoroughly to understand what actions they undertook to institutionalise them in their institutions and what best practises can be extracted thereof. The information incorporates several sources, including also the preliminary analysis reported in the TIME4CS proposal, and it is based on activities such as the Front Runners Workshop held on April 13, 2021, and individual exchanges and conversations carried out with representatives of each organisation. In the workshop, each FR presented its institution and its historical background of CS, and gave an overview of what GAs they applied and how successfully they were.

In a first step the gathered information has been analysed in the way that each FR’s actions have been assigned to our existing GAs. In a second step we identified new GAs that FRs have successfully applied but that were not in the original set of GAs. In the third step the original and new GAs have been evaluated and best practices have been extracted.

2. Front Runners

This chapter features an introduction of the three FR Organisations, presenting for each a short overview of the history of their CS and PES activities (which will be further detailed and classified according to the related GAs in Chapter 3).

2.1 University College London (UCL)

UCL is one of the world's leading research universities. Established in 1826, and recently grown to be the biggest university in London. It prides itself in being a leading multidisciplinary university, with strong records in various disciplines ranging from engineering, physical sciences, health and medical research to social sciences and humanities. UCL has more than 13,000 staff and 42,000 students from 150 different countries.

History of Citizen Science at UCL: UCL has a long history of doing interdisciplinary and participatory research and activities. It has adopted CS and OS in multiple areas. **In Research**, the Department of Geography, for instance, engaged in the 1980's with communities in the Environment and Society Research Unit. This includes valuing nature through focus groups with women from minority groups in East London and a wide range of deliberative and inclusionary research projects. UCL was also one of the institutions that participated in the Open Air Laboratories (OPAL³) project from 2007 to 2019. Since 2010 UCL has been home to the Extreme Citizen Science group (ExCiteS⁴), which is one of the leading groups in Europe that is dedicated to CS. ExCiteS brings together scholars from diverse fields to develop and contribute to the guiding theories, tools and methodologies that will enable any community to start a CS project to deal with issues that concern them. Another example is the Co-production Collective⁵ that supports co-production projects. The UCL Institute for Global Prosperity is also developing innovative citizen social science methods, and research into the role of digital technologies in citizen science is carried out in UCL Interaction Centre (UCLIC). **In Education and Awareness**, UCL launched in 2017 and is running one of the first full graduate level courses on CS, which is also available freely online on the remote learning platform UCL eXtend. UCL will soon start its first postgraduate programme in CS in 2022. **In Policy and Assessment**, UCL integrated OS into its promotion criteria with an explicit element of PES and also into PhD training. Moreover, it established a university-wide OS policy and organizes an annual OS Day.

2.2 Aarhus University (AU)

Established in 1928, AU has since developed into a major Danish university with a strong international reputation across the entire research spectrum. AU is a top ten university among universities founded within the past 100 years. It has a long tradition of partnerships with some of the world's best research institutions

³ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/opal/>

⁴ <https://www.geog.ucl.ac.uk/research/research-centres/excites/about-us>

⁵ <https://www.coproductioncollective.co.uk/>

and university networks. AU has a strong commitment to the development of society that is realized through its collaboration with government agencies and institutions, the business community, and citizens. This is also reflected in AU's mission that includes beside the common pillars of research and education also collaboration - so the interdisciplinary research to address societal changes.

History of CS at AU: In Research, there were early amateur research initiatives at AU, primarily in the fields of biology and archaeology. In the Mols Laboratory⁶ - a field research station owned by the Museum of Natural History Aarhus - biological research has been conducted in informal collaborations with local amateurs since 1941. Also, in 1981 a long-time collaboration between amateur and professional AU archaeologists was formalised in the establishment of the "East-Jutlandian Amateur Archaeologists" organisation. In 2017, AU researchers launched the DIME project⁷ (Digital Metal Detector Findings), which is one the largest projects for CS archaeology in the world. Furthermore, AU is home to "The Danish Center for Research Analysis and Research Policy"⁸ where researchers since the 1990's have performed meta-research in CS-related issues, such as science citizenship and public participation in science. Today, AU researchers across the five faculties have implemented CS as a research methodology. The Center for Science Studies⁹ (CSS) in the Faculty of Natural Sciences, is a research and teaching unit with strong competencies in science communication, CS, and the history and philosophy of science. CSS hosts a Master's programme in science studies with CS components and currently leads research projects dealing with CS, public understanding of science, philosophy of science, sociology of science, and environmental history. CSS is a core partner to the Danish network on CS and currently employs the network's coordinator. In 2021, CSS organizes the AU network on citizen science. **In Education**, CSS runs a Master's-level CS course and offers supervision for students specialising in CS. Moreover, CSS is responsible for teaching research integrity and responsible research and innovation to all PhD students at the Faculty of Natural Sciences. The teaching practices of CSS are supported by the Department of Mathematics and its Teaching Committee, and also by the Faculty's Study Board.

2.3 Citizen Science Center Zürich (CC-CS)

CC-CS is a Competence Center established in 2017 as a joint initiative of ETH Zurich (ETHZ) and the University of Zurich (UZH). It is a unique one-stop-shop supporting CS in Zurich and beyond by providing the resources, expertise and technical know-how to develop, set up, and run CS projects while maintaining the highest standards of excellence in research methodology. To enable researchers and citizens to co-create and conduct CS projects that produce academic quality scientific knowledge, the Center provides support in key areas such as tools and infrastructure (including open web and mobile platforms), methodology (easily accessible set of protocols and procedures, including aspects of data quality, research ethics, and more), and community management (support with creating and nurturing an engaged community of citizens and

⁶ <https://www.naturhistoriskmuseum.dk/mols-laboratory>

⁷ <https://arts.au.dk/en/news-and-events/news/show/artikel/nyt-digitalt-vaerktoej-vaekker-begejstring-blandt-metaldetektorbrugere/>

⁸ <https://ps.au.dk/en/research/research-centres/the-danish-centre-for-studies-in-research-and-research-policy/>

⁹ <https://css.au.dk/en/>

scientists). For teaching and training purposes, the Center has established the Participatory Science Academy¹⁰ (Partizipative Wissenschaftsakademie – PWA), that also provides Seeds Grants for project development.

The Center was originally planned, proposed and later founded by a group of professors of the two universities with a keen interest and practical experience in CS. One of them was Kevin Schawinski, the creator of the CS project Galaxy Zoo¹¹. The others had been focussing mainly in participatory research for health. The importance of such “CS champions” is crucial in the history of the CC-CS.

History of CS at CC-CS and UZH/ETHZ: CC-CS was only founded in 2017, but the history of CS at UZH and ETHZ started beforehand. **In Research**, UZH and ETHZ have a strong track record of CS conducted by its researchers. As an example, an exhibition recently showcased 19 CS projects at the two universities in the areas of language, cosmos, nature and landscape, mankind and health, history and digitization¹². In November 2015 the two universities, together with the University of Geneva, organized an international conference on “Standards and Recommendations for Citizen Science”. During and after the event, a group of Citizen Science specialists from Switzerland and Europe worked on the standards for Citizen Science and on policy recommendations. The work was published in 2016 as a LERU Advice Paper titled “Citizen science at universities: Trends, guidelines and recommendations”¹³ which has successfully served as inspiration to many European Universities. **In Education and Awareness**, CC-CS has been very proactive in reaching out to the local community of both researchers and citizens. It also provides, via its PWA, courses and training material for practitioners at all levels. **For Support Resources and Infrastructure**, CC-CS developed a web infrastructure that includes a platform featuring several ongoing institutional projects¹⁴ (linguistics, global health, biodiversity) and a CS Project Builder¹⁵, that allows open and easy implementation of data analysis CS pilots and test projects. The Center is also developing a smartphone App for data collection.

¹⁰ <https://www.pwa.uzh.ch/en.html>

¹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Galaxy_Zoo

¹² <https://www.grc.uzh.ch/en/focus/exhibition/CitizenScience.html>

¹³ <https://www.leru.org/publications/citizen-science-at-universities-trends-guidelines-and-recommendations>

¹⁴ <https://citizenscience.ch/>

¹⁵ <https://lab.citizenscience.ch/en/>

3. Grounding Action analysis

The following chapter examines in detail each of the grounding actions and the related practices and activities of the FR institutions.

3.1 Grounding Actions for Research

The Intervention Area “Research” is defined in Section 1.1 Intervention Areas (IAs) as “Acknowledgment by the RPOs ecosystem of CS as an evolving set of research methods and of its societal and educational benefits, through use of CS in research projects and creation of CS communities of practice”. The GAs identified for this area are described in the following, together with the associated experience of FRs and their experienced/perceived effectiveness.

3.1.1 Action: develop research projects using CS methodology

Having some direct experience with CS projects is extremely valuable, as promoting a research methodology without experience on the actual practice may be hardly convincing. Developing CS projects “beginning to end” provides invaluable first-hand experience and a body of knowledge that increases credibility when asking for Institutional Change.

FR Experience

All Front Runner institutions have direct experience with CS projects, sometimes dating back many years.

UCL researchers have ran several projects employing CS methodology across all different disciplines. As an example, in the digital humanities, the project Transcribe Bentham¹⁶ launched in 2009 has crowdsourced for more than a decade volunteers to transcribe the manuscripts written by Jeremy Bentham, one of the intellectual founders of UCL. Other important projects have been developed in the social sciences, like the Prosperity Co-Lab Kenya¹⁷ by the Institute of Global Prosperity; in the natural sciences, the Open Air Laboratories (OPAL); in engineering, OpenStreetMap¹⁸; and in medical sciences and epidemiology, the project ActEarly¹⁹, a collaborative approach for the early promotion of good health and wellbeing.

AU as well has a long-lasting experience with projects in multiple domains, including DIME²⁰(one of the biggest archaeological CS project in the world, with 2600 ‘amateur’ archaeologists recording archaeological metal detector findings) and the new ‘The sound of the Capital’²¹ (crowdsourcing sounds) in the Arts; ScienceAtHome²² started in quantum physics and then expanded into the social citizen sciences to study

¹⁶ http://transcribe-bentham.ucl.ac.uk/td/Transcribe_Bentham

¹⁷ <https://www.procolkenya.com/>

¹⁸ <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

¹⁹ <https://actearly.uk/>

²⁰ <https://www.metaldetektorfund.dk/>

²¹ <https://byhistorie.dk/forskning/igangvaerende-forskningsprojekter/lyden-af-hovedstaden/>

²² <https://www.scienceathome.org/>

human behaviours in a community of >300.000 game players; in Biology, Havblitz²³ (using eDNA to investigate the biology of the sea and involving 400 volunteers in environmental monitoring); in Health, different projects under the “Give Youth a Voice”²⁴ co-creation effort, that unites researchers and >300 young people around mental health, personal data and fake news; in the technical sciences, BioScience projects include government–related programmes to collect Hunter statistics on birds²⁵ and game that was launched in 1970, and the recent Mapping wolves in Denmark.

CC-CS is active in linguistics with the Wenker²⁶ project (transcribe and translate historical handwritten document in Swiss German), in biodiversity monitoring with Weasel Wanted (monitor weasels in the Swiss Midlands), in health with the SnakeID²⁷ Challenges (a collaboration with the World Health Organisation to tackle the global venomous snakebite crises). The University of Zurich has also a long tradition in participatory research in psychology and in the field of aging.

3.1.2 Action: expand running research projects using CS methodology

In any institution there may be ongoing research projects that, while being already effective with a traditional methodology, could be significantly expanded in scope by the contribution of citizens. Integrating CS in these projects is an effective way to show the unique impact of participatory approaches.

FR experience

At UCL many projects have benefited from the longstanding culture of CS practice. In 2012, UCL researchers of the London Nanotechnology Center crowdsourced volunteers for activities of image classification within the Feynman's Flowers project. This was the first project of its kind in the area of physics, in which citizens helped scientists to translate thousands of Scanning Tunnelling Microscope (STM) images.

Since its creation CC-CS has been contacted by several pre-existing projects for technical support with participative tools, and assistance with issues of community management and communication. Even if some of the support wasn't necessarily within the canonical use and definition of the methodology (one project was, for instance, a downloadable software to contribute film-based research on colours) the Center decided to support – as much as resources allow – all sort of participatory aspects to research as a strategy to prove their usefulness in the first phase of existence.

3.1.3 Action: establish/belong to a CS network (international or national associations)

The international community of CS practitioners is organized in international networks and associations, such as the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA²⁸), the Citizen Science Association in the US (CSA²⁹),

²³ <https://www.dn.dk/om-os/projekter-og-kampagner/havblitz/>

²⁴ <https://givdeungeordnet.dk/>

²⁵ <https://fauna.au.dk/en/hunting-and-game-management/wing-survey/>

²⁶ <https://wenker.citizenscience.ch/en/>

²⁷ <https://snakes.citizenscience.ch/>

²⁸ <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/>

²⁹ <https://citizenscience.org/>

Australian CS Associations (ACSA³⁰), and the more recent CS Asia and CS Africa. These often complement, and sometimes include, national and local CS networks (such as the German, Austrian and Danish CS networks) and other networks of similar scope, such as academic (LERU) and data-focused (CODATA³¹ - Committee on Data for Science and Technology). Additional opportunities of networking are provided within communities that generate around platforms (SciStarter³²) or movements (OS). These networks provide invaluable opportunities for sharing of knowledge and experiences, and an extraordinary stage for increased visibility of any RPOs activities.

FR experience

All FRs are actively involved in the activities of existing networks, and sometimes they have contributed in an operational way to their establishment. UCL researchers and students belong to different CS associations around the globe and have contributed to develop and coordinate ECSA's activities. UCL is also pushing the CS agenda in comparable networks, such as LERU and LIBER (Europe's research library community). CC-CS is currently a key player in the establishment of the CS Global Partnership, a "network of networks" of CS researchers and practitioners that aims at promoting and advancing CS for a sustainable world.

AU is currently hosting the coordinator of the national Danish CS network³³, and CC-CS is drafting, in collaboration with other Swiss Institutions, a "Swiss CS roadmap" till 2025 and beyond.

Representatives of the FR are – and have been – holding formal roles in some of the networks, such as Member of Advisory Board, Members of Board of Directors, Chair of Working Groups and Task Forces, etc.

3.1.4 Action: plan or implement changes in organisational structures or functions

For many existing RPOs, CS and other R&I activities may not have a natural place to be structurally integrated. Integration may require innovations in the organisational structure or flexibility in the use of certain existing bodies. This challenge is common to all sorts of Institutional Changes and innovation, namely the struggle of finding a place, entity or body within the organisation that would allow the implementation while minimising the need for creating new entities, with related additional costs in terms of time and resources.

FR experience

After years of discussion, and in line with the recommendations of the LERU "Roadmap for Open Science"³⁴ in 2020 UCL established the Office for Open Science, in charge of working on the eight pillars of OS, and where CS is recognized as one of these important pillars. The Office of Open Science, located at UCL Library Services, operates with a small team of experts who support researchers and students of all UCL departments. By locating the Office for Open Science in the Library, it is expected that the use of CS

³⁰ <https://citizenscience.org.au/>

³¹ <https://codata.org/>

³² <https://scistarter.org/>

³³ <https://citizenscience.dk/>

³⁴ <https://www.leru.org/publications/open-science-and-its-role-in-universities-a-roadmap-for-cultural-change>

methodologies will become just another way to perform research across all institutions, helping researchers and students to overcome the difficulty in the creation of interdisciplinary CS activities.

The CC-CS in Zurich was established as a “Competence Center”, a well-established way for Swiss research institutions to support multi-institutional collaborations, with the goal of bringing together in one place extensive expertise in a certain field. However, Competence Centers are not permanent entities, having a maximum lifetime of eight years during which one of the tasks is – if deemed necessary – to find long-term solutions and alternative forms of establishment and (self-)support.

3.2 Grounding Actions for Education & Awareness

The second IA identified by the TIME4CS consortium reads “Activities to raise awareness and build capacity amongst researchers, funders and civil society of criteria for successful CS activities in compliance with ethical, legal and privacy regulations. This includes events to promote CS and training programmes within the RPOs (also by establishing links with existing EU projects and training programmes on CS).”

3.2.1 Action: set up training programmes for researchers, students, and citizen scientists

Training programs are essential to get potential and current practitioners accustomed to the multiple ways and approaches of CS. A solid knowledge of all steps involved in designing and running a CS research project is at the base of generating high quality data and results, features that are essential to any mainstream research methodology. Training programs can take many forms and often include different kinds of theoretical and hands-on activities.

FR experience

The experience of UCL in integrating CS and education can be tracked back to 2007, when UCL researchers from different domains took part in the Open Air Laboratories (OPAL) initiative which was aimed at school children. Aiming to get the public more involved with nature, the initiative developed a range of local and national activities, not only encouraging people to spend more time outdoors, but also developing innovative educational programmes accessible to all ages and abilities, increasing the general understanding of the environment. OPAL was the first opportunity that many academics had to experiment with CS as an innovative methodology in education.

More programmes have followed targeted to researchers and students. The “Introduction to Citizen Science & Scientific Crowdsourcing” is offered to Geography Masters Students (for credits), but also available as a free open online course to everyone else. “Community Based Research: Getting Started” has been developed by the Institute of Global Prosperity - RELIEF Centre and is suitable for all academic researchers and teachers, students and NGOs who want to carry out community research and investigate relationships between schools and communities.

AU training activities are more recent. They include RRI and research integrity courses offered to all PhD students at the Faculty of Natural Sciences. At Master level, a full course on CS is run every two years, and a

CS component is offered in a Master's programme in science studies. A CS workshop run in October 2020 was specifically targeted to researchers.

One of the early successes of the CC-CS was the awarding by a Swiss Foundation of an additional, independent grant to establish the Participatory Science Academy (PWA) to develop teaching activity for ETHZ/UZH students. The academy has developed 15 courses with different formats, including introductory and advanced courses for doctoral students and postdocs (for example "Introduction to Citizen Science" and "Citizen Science Advanced"), but also for researchers and citizens, including an annual Citizen Science School. A particular activity of the PWA includes awarding seed grants to a number of projects that are supported both financially and with know-how and tools.

CC-CS has also provided an increasing number of ad-hoc lectures, presentations and workshops at domain-specific symposiums and conferences, responding to invitations by departments and research groups wishing to familiarise themselves with the methodology and tools offered by the Center.

3.2.2 Action: establish or link with working groups on CS

The CS networks mentioned above (see Subsection 3.1.4 Action: plan or implement changes in organisational structures or functions) provide a platform for sharing of experience and knowledge, but also exceptional opportunities for joint and wide-reaching research with and about the methodology, and working groups focussing on a broad spectrum of CS-related topics.

FR experience

Researchers from all FRs are involved in existing Working Groups (WG) and Task Forces (TF) that tackle aspects of the methodology and its uptake. This includes for example the ECSA WG on CS in Universities and the one on CS for Health, and the group that supports national CS initiatives, currently focusing on criteria for CS platforms. UCL is very active in ongoing work internationally, AU researchers participate in the CSA working group on education, and in the Danish CS Network WG on Biodiversity, climate and environment. CC-CS co-chairs the CODATA WG on CS for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG).

3.2.3 Action: organize debates or public events to promote CS

Reaching out to (potential and existing) non-academic practitioners, and more broadly to the general public, requires a particular effort by academics and research organisations that need to develop dedicated occasions of exchange and interactions. The format and content of such events, including language, required basic skills, and background knowledge, need to be especially tailored to this (sometimes challenging!) target audience.

FR experience

UCL offers students and researchers different opportunities to engage with the communities and promote CS, and has done a lot of work with school children and disadvantaged communities, including but not limited

to the work done within the OPAL initiative mentioned in the Subsection 3.1.1 Action: develop research projects using CS methodology.

AU researchers participate in the yearly Danish Science Festival, and collaborated in organising the first public DK CS Symposium in 2019. Funds are already secured for a proper CS conference in 2022, organised by AU, which will include a Citizens' Day featuring CS projects to the public. AU also works with school children and high school students through the ScienceAtHome and Give Youth a Voice initiatives.

CCCS has been actively participating in university-wide and Zurich-wide public events such as Scientifica 2019 (coming up again in September 2021), has joined public debates such as "Pint of Science", has organized public lecture series such as "Citizen Science – potentials for transformative science" (2019), and the first "Swiss CS conference" in 2021, open to all practitioners for academia and not.

3.2.4 Action: set up informal occasion of interactions with researchers

Researchers practicing CS are often operating in different domains, and hence departments, with little occasions for exchanges and interactions. While formal presentations, conferences, WGs are essential to generating such opportunities, official events often have very structured agendas and interactions, and a focus on specific fields/domains that may limit the diversity of experience of the participants. Providing less formal occasions, where researchers from multiple fields are invited and encouraged to share their experience with CS (including successes, failures, and questions), is an effective way to strengthen researchers' confidence and adoption of the CS methodology.

FR experience

Within the EU DITOs project³⁵, UCL has organized and carried out several informal activities to engage academics and introduce CS to researchers. Also, along the years, UCL students and researchers have launched and participated in different Citizen Science Meetup strategies around London, including Science has no borders (2018) and "Meeting the South-East Citizen Science community" in 2019. Also, some postdoc students, have started a mapping exercise of CS activities to raise awareness and build connections on CS activities.

An internal AU CS Network is in the initial phases, but the first meeting has had to be postponed twice due to covid-19. It is now scheduled for August 2021 and many researchers have already indicated their support for and willingness to participate in the initiative.

CC-CS is actively nurturing its community of UZH and ETHZ researchers by providing regular meetup opportunities both in-person and virtual (condition permitting), knowledge exchange channels, and opportunities of collaboration. This includes Brown Bag Lunches (every two months), blog hosting, joint work on documents of common interest (such as writing together the criteria that regulate the support for new projects). In January 2020 the initiative "Open House" at the Center, which wanted to propose regular

³⁵ <http://www.togetherscience.eu/about>

occasions for anybody interested to mingle at the Center's office, was launched but soon interrupted by the pandemic after the first happening.

3.2.5 Action: set up info sessions specifically for management

Securing the attention of members of the institutional management, including head of departments, deans of faculties, and others, requires as well a particular effort and the development of dedicated occasions of exchange and interactions. In this case, however, a lot is at stake concerning the establishment and long-term support of CS in the institution, and generating CS "evangelists" (or champions, as we will see later) by making them aware and knowledgeable about the methodology is strategic to obtain support for successful institutional integration.

FR experience

To increase the outreach of CS within the academic community, and especially at the management level, UCL has run information sessions as part of the outreach strategy of the Office of Open Science and Scholarship. The "lightening talks" organized by the Office, have demonstrated through concrete examples the breath that CS can give to research projects at UCL.

3.2.6 Action: find and nurture "CS champions" both at the management level and at the student/researcher level

In today's business environment, a "change champion" is an individual, often at the managerial level, who sees the need and has a vision for change, and actively advocates for it and facilitates it. This is not different for Institutional Change within RPOs. Here as well, CS "champions" are necessary to advocate for and promote the methodology from within, and create institutional support. They are instrumental to the concrete implementation by endorsing the vision and motivating others to overcome potential barriers.

Champions do not need to be only from the management, they can be from any level within the Institution. In fact, it is recommended to have champions from multiple levels that can advocate on different fronts, from students and young researchers all the way to full professors and heads of research groups.

FR experience

UCL has several champions at the management level, who from their different departments have advocated for the inclusion and development of CS methodologies within the institution. Some not exhaustive examples of the many UCL champions are Dr Paul Ayris, Vice-Provost for UCL Library Services and head of the UCL Office for Open Science and Scholarship; Prof. Anna Cox (UCL-Interaction Centre) Vice Dean for Equality, Diversity & Inclusion who has been directly involved with different aspects of crowdsourcing; and Muki Haklay (UCL- Department of Geography), Co-director of the Extreme Citizen Science Group. Many UCL students have also devoted their efforts towards the use of CS strategies, and UCL recognises their work via

the Beacon Bursary funding scheme which provides financial support to allow PhD students and staff to perform public engagement activities.

AU has a number of informal CS Champions across all five faculties, including Associate professor Kristian Hvidtfelt Nielsen and postdoc Gitte Kragh in the Faculty of Natural Sciences who focus on supporting AU CS researchers, staff and students through establishment of an AU CS Network as well as teaching CS; Professor Jacob Sherson at the Faculty of Business and Social Sciences and Natural Sciences who has run the online crowdsourcing CS platform ScienceAtHome since 2013; Associate professor Andres Dobat at the Faculty of Arts who runs the Danish Metal Detector Finds (DIME) archaeological CS project which is one of the largest archaeological CS projects in the world; Professor Carsten Obel at the Faculty of Health who champions involving the public, especially youth, in research projects such as Give Youth a Voice; Assistant professor Qian Janice Wang at the Faculty of Technical Sciences also champions CS for sensory and consumer science and support other researchers through CS workshops; Head of Engagement Linda Greve at the Science Museums also supports CS at all levels; and finally, librarian Tine Legarth Iversen at AU Library champions Open Science, including CS, among students and researchers through supporting them in their projects.

CC-CS has the advantage of having been founded by champions at both UZH and ETHZ. The original founders and Board of Directors included experts in participatory approaches to research, such as, among others, Prof. M. Martin and former Prof. D. Wyler of UZH, and Prof. E. Hafen, Prof. E. Vayena and Prof. M. Ristow of ETH Zurich, all effective evangelists of the methodology. Kevin Schawinski, former professor at ETHZ Institute for Astronomy, is the founder of Galaxy Zoo, one of the most successful CS projects to date. The Center is also actively nurturing its community of local researchers; among them, some of the more vocal are, as one can easily imagine, the ones that have been running successful projects thanks to the multiple forms of support offered by the Center.

3.2.7 Action: develop easily accessible materials (prints, web, media, ...)

Easily accessible information about CS methodology, tools, best practices, etc., clearly benefits all audiences of current and potential practitioners, and facilitates understanding and uptake – which in turn builds support at all levels.

Exchange of knowledge within the organisation and with the members of the general public can happen in a variety of ways, including in person, via online platforms (websites and social media), and through printed materials. However, thanks to pervasive content proposed by social media platforms, we are all getting used to graphically pleasant presentations, short/clear messages, and seamless access, so CS material as well should try to be up to the current standards.

FR experience

All FRs are developing different kinds of resources about CS that can be found in multiple platforms. This includes MOOCs and online courses (publicly available on YouTube) offered by UCL, thematic essays in the form of blogs offered by UCL and CC-CS, and printed leaflets available for researchers, the public, and everybody interested.

CC-CS is currently working, together with their community of researchers, on a “CS Handbook” that will include practical advice on how to design, set up and run CS projects in Zurich and beyond.

3.3 Grounding Actions for Support Resources & Infrastructure

For what concerns different forms of support offered to researchers and development/availability of infrastructures, this IA includes “Creation within the RPOs of a single point of contact for addressing CS questions and of a system to support researchers implementing CS activities, including support to CS projects for long-term commitment for infrastructure and data repositories”.

3.3.1 Action: identify an institutional contact point for CS

Establishing a single-entry point, or “one-stop-shop”, is a well-known and effective business strategy that can usefully be adopted by research institutions when they want to provide convenience and efficiency to the organisation. For all stakeholders involved, at all levels of the institution and beyond, a single institutional point for “all things CS” can act both as a repository of knowledge and tools, and a pool of shared experiences and skills. In the long term, this choice can be strategic to optimise the use of all kinds of resources.

FR experience

In UCL, CS happened in an organic and truly bottom-up manner. Working groups such as RELIEF (Research, Education, Learning, Information Technology, and Entrepreneurship for the Future) within the Institute for Global Prosperity and ExCiteS were created to work with the local needs and practices to co create research practices that could³⁶. Over the time, researchers from the different areas and departments joined forces to share and find support for their CS interests, projects and needs. As of 2020, the Office of Open Science and Scholarship has taken over the leading role of integrating the accumulated CS knowledge and support all different departments interested to engage in CS activities.

At AU, the organisation of CS activities and projects is also happening in an organic and bottom-up approach. The AU Library offers some support to researchers and students interested in CS, as well does the AU CS Network.

The CC-CS, on the contrary, was a top-down, institutional initiative, established with the clear mandate to play this “one-stop-shop” role. From the start, it has been offering support in four areas, namely tools (including platforms for data collection and analysis), CS methodology (including coaching and teaching), community management (including also communication), and partnerships/networking opportunities.

In 2018, the Center established the PWA, a second entry point dedicated specifically to offering teaching courses and training opportunities to students, researchers, and local practitioners.

³⁶ <https://www.geog.ucl.ac.uk/research/research-centres/excites>

3.3.2 Action: develop protocols on implementation of CS activities

Sometimes moving from theory to practice can be tricky, especially when adopting a research methodology that involves areas often new to traditional research (such as, for example, the involvement of non-professional researchers). In this case, the availability of clear protocols, to-do lists and guidelines may significantly help adoption at all levels.

FR experience

CC-CS has taken the approach to develop some of the key processes of the Center in close collaboration with the community of interested researchers, using an iterative process based on in-person interactions (such as dedicated Brown Bag Lunches) and work on shared documents. This concerned especially the process that can be defined “institutional”, such as deciding which projects should be supported and their priorities, and what are the steps for evaluation and implementation of any given project. The result of this work includes a set of agreed criteria for project support, and a “projects pipe-line” that clarifies in a schematic way the interactions with the Center.

CC-CS is currently working, together with their community of researchers, on a “CS Handbook” that will include practical advice on how to design, set up and run – with the support of the Center - CS projects in Zurich and beyond.

3.3.3 Action: provide ethic/legal protocols tailored to the institutions/national requirements

Among the protocols just mentioned (Subsection 3.3.2 Action: develop protocols on implementation of CS activities), legal and ethical guidelines stand out because of their perceived (and often real) complication. In fact, regulations and processes are different depending on each institution’s ethical committee, which in turn follows country-level directives. On top of those, especially for data protection and privacy, comes the EU with its own General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and, depending on where the data are stored (i.e. servers in the US), potentially more.

FR experience

As all universities and research institutions, UCL, AU and CC-CS (UZH/ETHZ) have their own ethical committees and data protection and privacy teams to help researchers navigate the process of handling data correctly and, when needed, obtain the necessary permissions. However, in the experience of the FRs, these teams are mainly concerned with protecting health related data and are used to considering citizens as “subjects of research” (patients) and not as co-researchers. So, a dialogue is necessary to make them aware of the potential issues and specific needs of CS projects.

The dialogue is ongoing. At UCL, as more applications for CS project clearance come in, ethic and data committees are starting to develop guidelines that take into consideration the requirements of CS initiatives.

CC-CS commissioned an Ethic officer to write a report³⁷ that, starting from the point of research oversight in the Swiss context, gives an overview of existing ethics guidelines in CS as promoted by CSA, ECSA and similar organisations. It highlights the relative lack of attention to ethical governance and processes in current CS guidelines and recommends setting up an intra-institutional process to deal with ambiguities in the future.

3.3.4 Action: foresee funds for CS activities

Researchers often struggle with finding financial support for their projects, even more so in the case of experimenting with innovative methodologies. While big initiatives, involving multiple research groups and partners, can request grants at the national Science Foundation's level, or to the European Commission, small size and exploratory projects have few options. Providing funds for such endeavours, typically in the form of small grants, can be vital for such projects.

FR experience

UCL provides funds for CS activities via different grant schemes. Via "Train and Engage" at the Public Engagement Unit, UCL provides postgraduate research students with public engagement workshops alongside the opportunity to apply for funding of up to £1000 to run projects. The Beacon Bursaries fund is available to UCL staff and postgraduate research students, with awards of up to £2,000 to advance the practice and culture of public and community engagement within UCL. The "Grand Challenges" support interdisciplinary programmes in the areas of Global Health, Sustainable Cities, Human Wellbeing, Cultural Understanding, Justice & Equality, and Transformative Technology (the six Grand Challenges). They include small grants for grass-roots cross-disciplinary collaborations and small grants (up to £2,000) for doctoral students from different faculties for research-informed, societally relevant, cross-disciplinary. The French Embassy's Department of Science & Technology offers funding for UCL researchers to organise workshops in collaboration with research institutions in France.

At AU, the AU Research Foundation provides funding for research and research network activities. Also, the EarlyCash programme managed by The Kitchen (an AU open public space and café to facilitate collaboration) offers seed money for various activities that involve collaboration with external stakeholders.

The PWA at CC-CS supports a limited number of "Seed Grants" projects financially, and with know-how and tools. The funding, provided by a local Swiss Foundation (Mercator Foundation) allows giving out seed grants for a maximum of 50'000 CHF /project. Through the PWA, CC-CS has developed and organized the application and review processes. As of April 2021, 16 projects are funded.

3.3.5 Action: establish facilities to support CS activities

In this context of CS supporting actions, the term "facilities" refers both to physical places where different stakeholders can meet and interact in person in an environment that is conceived to serve and support co-research activities, and virtual environments and platforms with the same exact goals.

³⁷ <https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch/handle/20.500.11850/428502>

FR experience

In terms of physical spaces, UCL has established a Masters students led version of “science shops” via the Community Research Initiative for Students (CRIS). CRIS offers to focus the master’s dissertation work on CS for real community needs by building connections with London’s voluntary sector.

CC-CS strategic location downtown Zurich provides a comfortable place for meetings open to practitioners.

3.3.6 Action: make known and available open and free tools and/or existing tech solution

Making technological choices (i.e., selecting tools and infrastructure that will enable and support the research process) is one of the most challenging parts of designing any (CS) research project. This choice has numerous and long-lasting repercussions on resources and long-term sustainability of the project (personnel, skills, timeline, budget). Leveraging existing open and free tools and infrastructures facilitates the task enormously, especially considering that many of such solutions have been developed with the specific needs of CS in mind, and they have been used and perfected over time thanks to the feedback of researchers and volunteer contributors.

FR experience

UCL has been advocating for open crowdsourcing platforms since 2004, when one of its students developed OpenStreetMap, the “wikipedia of mapping”, a platform to allow anyone to contribute to mapping efforts worldwide. ExCiteS has also been very productive in the development of open tools for public participation, including Mapping for Change (2008), a participatory mapping platform that visualises user generated data, and Sapelli (2017), a mobile data collection and sharing platform designed for non-literate and illiterate users with little or no prior ICT experience.

AU Library offers freely available CS know-how (in Danish) to students, researchers, and others. The Open Innovation in Science has developed an Open Science platform used to facilitate collaboration between university and industry³⁸. The Centre for Science Studies has published a mapping of the Danish CS landscape, which can be used as an inspiration catalogue and is available in open access (in Danish)³⁹.

CC-CS as well has been active in building a virtual infrastructure that supports researchers and the public in the implementation and running of CS projects. In particular, the offering includes a web platform (CS Project Builder) where anybody can build a “data analysis CS project” (projects where contributors, via a web interface, perform complex classifications and tagging of digital data) quickly and without need for any coding skills, and a smartphone app generator (CS Logger) that allows the design of Apps for data collection tailored to a project’s specific needs.

³⁸ <https://spoman-os.org/>

³⁹ <https://unipress.dk/udgivelser/c/citizen-science-i-danmark>

On top of in-house developed offering, and considering that it would be impossible for such solutions to cover all possible project requirements, FRs found it effective to provide knowledge (and potentially support) for the use of the many other tools available in the wider crowdsourcing and CS networks.

3.3.7 Action: facilitate the setup of pilots/tests for the methodology (newly added)

Actions 3.3.4 and 3.3.6 can also be interpreted as an encouragement for researchers that experiment with CS to “start small” by setting up pilots and tests for their project ideas. Researchers are increasingly solicited, thanks to the structure of grant-giving organisations such as EU and National Science Foundations, to plan full-flagged research projects from the start, spending significant time and resources upfront, often without the opportunity to run tests and collect data to support their assumptions, methods and plans. By providing small seed grants and the proper infrastructure, CS project proponents have the possibility to strengthen their proposals with results obtained by running pilots and tests.

FR experience

UCL’s Beacon Bursaries for Public Engagement has been providing financial support for more than 12 years to researchers and students aiming to advance the practice and culture of public and community engagement. This funding scheme enables UCL staff and postgraduate students to pilot mutually beneficial engagement activities that can include CS between communities and UCL research and teaching.

3.3.8 Action: participate in national or international CS projects (E.g. H2020) (newly added)

The kind of network, knowledge and opportunities provided by national or international CS projects, such as the ones supported by national Science Foundations and the EU, are unique and owed to the size and variety of skills and experiences offered by the diverse partners (from both public and private sectors) which make up these big consortiums.

FR experience

Thanks to the early establishment of ExCiteS, UCL has been involved in EU projects since 2011, starting with what was at the time the EU Seventh Framework Programme (FP7). UCL has been involved in projects that use CS as a way of doing research but also projects where different aspects of CS methodology are the subject of the research. These include EveryAware (Enhance Environmental Awareness through Social information technologies, 2011 – 2014), Citizen Cyberlab (2012 – 2015), DitoS (Doing It Together Science, 2016 – 2019), ECSAnVis (Extreme Citizen Science: Analysis and Visualisation, 2016 – 2021), eu-citizen.science (2019 – 20121), and more.

At the national level, AU is involved in a number of projects, including a project focussing on the Roles of Research Libraries in CS, and in “Lakes in spare time”, a project initiated by South Denmark University to gather knowledge on water quality. In addition to TIME4CS, AU is involved in other EU H2020 projects including REGREEN (2019 – 2023) an EU project to promote urban liveability and involve local residents, and

the NewHoRRizon project (2017-2021), aiming at further integrating Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in the research and innovation systems nationally and internationally.

CC-CS is involved in three EU projects, namely TIME4CS, INCENTIVE (2021 – 2023) and CROWD4SDG (2020 – 2022). INCENTIVE has goals similar to TIME4CS, as it aims at “establishing citizen science hubs in European research performing and funding organisations to drive institutional change and ground responsible research and innovation in society”. CROWD4SDG aims at unleashing the potential of CS data to monitor the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

Nationally, CC-CS is part of the National Centre of Competence in Research (NCCR) “Evolving Language” that started in 2020 to research the evolution of language via an interdisciplinary approach that includes citizens in the research process. The Center is also supporting the University Research Priority Programme (URPP) Human Reproduction Reloaded (2021 - 2028), a project that will explore the rapidly changing medical technology on human reproduction and its implications.

3.4 Grounding Actions for Policy & Assessment

The fourth intervention area has many aspects in common with OS and very much shares some of the institutional challenges, as it refers to the “Assessment of CS contributions and adaptation of research evaluation policies and reputation systems accordingly, taking into account incentives which could foster the implementation of CS activities”.

3.4.1 Action: adopt evaluation criteria for researchers’ evaluation that take into account CS

The current criteria to evaluate researchers and the system of incentives is based on traditional research methodology, close and proprietary data, number of publications in high ranked reviews. To support researchers’ careers within CS, especially at early stages, it is essential to consider and give weight to aspects related to public participation and engagement.

FR experience

Thanks to the effort, among others, of the Public Engagement Unit, the UCL evaluation criteria already includes aspects of public engagement. One of the areas of activities considered during the assessment of the performance of researchers is “Enterprise and External Engagement”, which mentions in its description “*All promotion cases should emphasise the benefits of enterprise and external engagement to the discipline and to UCL as institution*”.

At AU as well this is happening already, with “Public Outreach” being part of the evaluation in the hiring process of permanent scientific staff. All research and public engagement activities, including CS, must also be registered in the AU PURE system, a Current Research Information System, and will then appear on the individual researcher's AU page and will be considered at the annual evaluation meetings with department heads.

CC-CS has run several workshops with Early Career Researcher during CS events to start tackling this issue in Zurich's institutions.

3.4.2 Action: install reward mechanisms for doing CS

Awards in particular are very effective incentives for single researchers and research groups, because the increased visibility provided by public awards increases in turn their reputation at the institutional, local, and potentially national level.

FR experience

UCL has put in place different mechanisms that reward the public engagement and social impact of students and researchers. In 2013 Mapping for Change won the UCL Social Enterprise Project of the Year Award, and in 2018 ExCiteS won Provost's Public Engagement Award.

3.4.3 Action: develop/adopt explicit mission statements and strategies

A significant step toward institutionalising CS is to explicitly mention it in official documents, including mission statements, institutional strategies, and/or institutional norms, regulations, policies and agreements. Until this happens, CS can hardly get any significant attention by the management as supporting it is not considered an institutional responsibility or priority.

FR experience

All FR institutions are actively working on their OS strategies and policies.

At UCL, CS is part of the mission statement of the UCL Office for Open Science and Scholarship, which mentions *"By adopting an Open Science strategy, UCL expects to open further the academic environment to members of the public – as their knowledge and insights are invaluable to informing the research process."* Work is also ongoing to include CS in the official strategy of UCL, and in other policies.

In Denmark, CS became known as a methodology only in the last ten years, though similar approaches were previously used, and it is not yet explicitly part of the AU strategy. However, AU's strategic plan [2025] for research excellence and collaboration with external partners and communities implicitly includes CS. According to the plan, AU aims to take responsibility for continued development of democracy and sustainability. In collaboration with society, AU contributes to economic growth and sustainable development, but also to develop dialogue between the university and society through public engagement and collaborative involvement with society. Collaboration is the third leg of AU's mission (the other two are research and education). Collaboration is specifically aimed at public authorities, businesses, NGOs, and secondary schools. Additionally, the Natural Sciences Faculty new Draft Strategy includes the aim to "Disseminate the concept of 'Open Science' to more subject areas", scheduled for 2023-2025.

The University of Zurich started in 2020 the work to define the UZH Open Science Policy, and the CC-CS has been invited to be part of the Task Force in charge of elaborating the policy. The document, which includes CS as part of "Open Research Processes", will be ratified in 2021.

4. Practical Recommendations

As illustrated in the evaluation of the GAs in Chapter 3, FRs have carried out the actions in slightly different ways, with tactics and methods that depend on their cultural, historical and scientific specificity. UCL for instance has a clear grassroots, bottom-up and organic approach to its evolution and achievements, while CC-CS methods and history show a structured, top-down, and carefully planned development. Their combined experience can be summarized in the following best practices.

Research

- Make sure to gain experience with CS projects. This can be at any level (i.e. designing and implementing projects from scratch or joining ongoing ones) and in any domain, as CS can be used throughout most disciplines in science and humanities.
- Look around in your organisation for existing projects. It may happen that their existence is not acknowledged as often researchers are not aware that what they are doing is already CS. Search for projects where CS and PES can naturally help.
- Widen the interpretation of CS and PES, by taking advantage of the existing network of practitioners to provide inspiring examples. Join ECSA or your national CS association if it exists, or at least be aware of their resources and activities. Visit existing platforms that feature all kinds of existing projects.

Education & Awareness

- Educate yourself first, by joining ongoing research work on the methodology, and sharing experiences with existing (network of) practitioners.
- Build momentum by educating the other stakeholders, starting with the ones inside the organisation and easier to reach, i.e. researchers and students. To be on board and support change, they have to be fully aware of the methodology and what it implies at all levels.
- Educate the management, it will require appropriate channels and tailored messages. Find champions at their level, so that they can be influenced by their peers.
- Reach out to the public with attractive and clear material, and with the media they naturally use. Without “citizens” there is no CS!

Support Resources & Infrastructure

- Support adoption by providing simple and practical guidelines, checklists, easy protocols and procedures.
- Provide technical solutions to the most common applications and projects. Educate yourself about the several open and free solutions that exist already and that can be adopted with very little or no development efforts.

- Try to avoid frustration in early adopters by encouraging the implementation of pilots before they invest lots of time and resources. If possible, provide small grants to encourage and facilitate adoption. Explore local foundations and organisations for additional support.
- Look for partnerships and collaboration, try to join EU consortiums in particular as they provide invaluable experience, connections and knowledge.

Policy & Assessment

- Be aware of the professional and career related needs of researchers, and help them advocate for incentives at the relevant bodies in your institutions.
- If possible, join working groups and task forces at your institution to document the presence and relevance of CS in official documents and strategies.

In addition, the analysis reveals a few underlining common traits and tactics that have enhanced the cumulative effect of each single action for all of the FR, and has helped the successful establishment of CS and PES in the FR institutions in a significant way. These winning approaches can be summarized as follows.

- **Being proactive**

Proactive reach is essential as occasions and opportunities for CS need to be actively searched for and created at the institutions. Sitting at the office and waiting for researchers to reach out is a luxury that only well-established entities (such as libraries for instance) can enjoy. Having a motivated and enthusiastic team is essential.

- **Choosing wisely early domains of activity**

Especially when introducing CS and PES activities in an Institution for the first time, it is worth maximizing the value of the results, both in terms of scientific results but also communication and visibility, by choosing carefully the area of activity. Engaging in scientific domains that have high status and relevance for the institution may increase interest and support (including integrating and enhancing existing initiatives).

- **Being “faculty independent”**

At the level of organisational structures or functions, locating CS in a place that is not bound to one specific faculty (for example the library) can help build a spirit of shared ownership throughout the Organisation.

- **Nurturing your community**

Community management is an essential part of practicing CS. Converting to the methodology students and researchers, and attracting and retaining the general public is essential for the success of projects and initiatives. An engaged community builds momentum toward institutional changes.

- **Boosting visibility and reputation of the institution**

All universities and research institutions worry about their local reputation and national and international ranking. These are increasingly dependent on – together with purely academic factors – new aspects such as sustainability, communication, social impact, etc. By organizing local events and presentations, and promoting the Institution's CS activities via social media and other communication channels, CS helps increase public interest and visibility. Similarly, being actively involved in national and international networks of research institutions offers unique opportunities to strengthen reputation, especially when associated with management/chair roles in such bodies. To this effect though, it is essential to keep the institutional communications offices aware and in the loop.

- **Building close connections with OS activities**

The OS movement is gaining real traction, and institutions worldwide just started rearranging their strategy and processes to include it. By being active participants in this process, and being clear on the role of CS in this global effort, CS can gradually gain visibility and consensus, and find in OS support structures a natural place to sit in any research institution.

5. Conclusion

This document presents the results of the analysis performed on the history and activities of the FR Organisations to extract relevant information concerning practices to promote and sustain CS and PES in RPOs. They highlight and provide evidence of the Institutional Changes necessary for such implementation. The analysis has generated a wealth of information that has been mapped and scrutinised in order to expand the knowledge related to Intervention Areas and Grounding Actions. The same information has then been consolidated and codified in the form of best practices which provide actionable advice for successful institutional adoption of CS.

This knowledge will be used as basis for the development of specific and tailored roadmaps for each of the implementing organisation. It can also support capacity building activities and provide content for mutual learning programmes.

APPENDIX

Table 1 - Overview of the Grounding Actions

Intervention Areas	Grounding Actions
Research	Acknowledgment by the RPOs ecosystem of CS as an evolving set of research methods and of its societal and educational benefits, through use of CS in research projects and creation of CS communities of practice.
	To develop research projects using CS methodology
	To expand running research projects using CS methodology
	To establish/belong to a CS network (international or national associations)
	To plan or implement changes in organisational structures or functions
Education & Awareness	Activities to raise awareness and build capacity amongst researchers, funders and civil society of criteria for successful CS activities in compliance with ethical, legal and privacy regulations. This includes events to promote CS and training programmes within the RPOs (also by establishing links with existing EU projects and training programmes on CS).
	To set up training programmes for researchers, students, and citizen scientists
	To establish or link with working groups on CS
	To organise debates or public events to promote CS
	To set up informal occasion of interactions with researchers
	To set up info sessions specifically for management
	To find and nurture “CS champions” at the management level
	To find and nurture “CS champions” at the student/researcher level
	To develop easily accessible materials (prints, web, media,...)
Support Resources & Infrastructure	Creation within the RPOs of a single point of contact for addressing CS questions and of a system to support researchers implementing CS activities, including support to CS projects for long-term commitment for infrastructure and data repositories.
	To identify an institutional contact point for CS
	To develop protocols on implementation of CS activities
	To provide ethic/legal protocols tailored to the institutions/national requirements
	To foresee funds for CS activities

	To establish facilities to support CS activities
	To make known and available open and free tools and/or existing tech solution
	To facilitate the setup of pilots/tests for the methodology
	To participate in national or international CS projects (e.g. H2020)
Policy & Assessment	Assessment of CS contributions and adaptation of research evaluation policies and reputation systems accordingly, taking into account incentives which could foster the implementation of CS activities.
	To adopt evaluation criteria for researchers' evaluation that take into account CS
	To install reward mechanisms for doing CS
	To adopt explicit mission statements and strategies
	To develop new institutional norms, regulations, policies or agreements